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ACTIVISM, EVENT AND THE TRANSMISSION OF BEHAVIOR DESIGNING WITH BEHAVIOR FOR BEHAVIOR

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ABSTRACT

In Helsinki, summer 2010, a group of friends challenged each other to just consume at local independent stores for two weeks long. This challenge became an event of public calling for controversy, rallying support for small independent shop owners, in opposition to large retail chains. This forms the premise of a case study, according which this paper will argue that the design of an event as such is not only relevant in forms of activism, but is also relevant for design in general, especially when design addresses behavior change or lifestyle change. A qualitative study based on Maffesoli's theory of neo-tribalism identifies this event as mediated and designed. Although more study is needed, this paper suggests that an event as such fosters a certain image, celebrates certain behavior and that it entails a behavior change for those that join it. As such, it is a powerful means for design when it comes to behavior change: **Designing with behavior for behavior.**

Keywords: Food consumption, activism, behavior change

INTRODUCTION

In Helsinki, summer of 2010, a challenge was called out within a group of friends: 'I challenge you all to just consume at local independent stores for two weeks long.' Something that started out as a private issue grew out to become a public concern and event. The event became a public calling for controversy, rallying support for small independent shop owners, in opposition to large retail chains. It attracted local media coverage and became a Facebook event that attracted almost a thousand participants.

With the suggested *Trajectory of Artificiality* Klaus Krippendorff observes in design a shift in emphasis from technological to human considerations or from hardware to information (Krippendorff, 1997). This shift holds consequences on the material that design works with. He speaks of design becoming increasingly concerned with the immaterial, handling abstract concepts, such as health or health behavior. Drawing from the anthropologist Levi-Strauss' idea of *bricolage*, Panagiotis Louridas describes design metaphorically as bricolage and the practice of design as creating or recreating metaphors. He illustrates this by comparison between the engineer and the designer. "The bricoleur makes do with what's there, with what he encounters. In that, he differs from the engineer: Whereas the engineer creates the means for the completion of his work, the bricoleur redefines the means that he already has" (Louridas, 1999). Panagiotis sees design as a tinkering, using means, or materials, which the designer cannot freely select. These materials have meanings, which the designer cannot freely specify. Meanings both limit and enable design. Considering design as an activity Panagiotis goes beyond the common understanding of it. The characterization of design as bricolage means that design is a distinctive humans activity, but not so distinct. With other words, design is a more common activity than is usually thought of. As an activity, design can be observed in everyday life, with people we do not commonly see as designers.

In "Participation in design things" Pelle Ehn re-addresses our understanding of the word "thing". He gives us a short etymological account on "things" and informs us "in pre-Christian Nordic and Germanic societies, things were the governing assemblies and places, where disputes were resolved" (Ehn, 2008). Things resolve around concerns and, drawing on

Bruno Latour's idea of socio-material assemblies, Ehn characterizes "things" as "collectives of humans and non-humans". In turn, "design things" would be concerned with making these things public. Ehn's idea around a "design thing" can be summarized as followed: A design thing is usually associated with matters of concern, and has the purpose of making this thing explicit and public, opening up for controversy.

This study considers this event just such a design thing, where a concern is made explicit and public, potentially inducing a certain behavior in people: A discursive space where one behavior is celebrated and others denounced. This study suggests that this event is designed with a certain behavior in mind and demonstrates it through those that behave that way, with the purpose to transmit this behavior to those that do not, yet. For this, this paper hopes to give new directions for research.

ACTIVISM AS FORM OF NEO-TRIBALISM AND BEHAVIOR

Heather Mair argues a relationship between social activism and leisure (Mair, 2002). Within the context of social activism she observes a trend she describes with the notion of civil leisure. This is when people choose to spend their free time in struggling for social justice and progressive change. In "The pleasure citizen" Sarah Riley explores leisure as a site for new forms of political participation (Riley, 2010). Making use of Maffesoli's concept of neo-tribalism, her studies propose that political participation may be occurring at an informal level through consumption. These are instances in which people created local and informal spaces of autonomy characterized by a celebration of community, sociality and hedonism. Her observations suggest a move from economic and consumer citizen subjects to the pleasure citizen.

It is in "Jeux de masques: postmodern tribalism", where Michel Maffesoli speaks of neo-tribalism for the first time (Maffesoli, 1988). He points out in the growth of mass society, the development of micro groups, to which he refers as tribes. In contrary to the modern idea of individualization, he observes, in these groupings, a form of de-individualization. Within such a tribe a person takes up a role and

becomes a subject that is driven by the group of which he or she is part. Maffesoli's approach is based on the twin assumption of 1) the multiplicity of the self and 2) the communal ambience that it instills. To give this more force he says that the person in such tribes, or the role one takes, is worthless except in relation to others and in relation to the idea that allows one to exist only in the spirit of others. It is such a context that encourages the emergence of a strong collective sentiment. Maffesoli's idea of de-individualization is inseparable from his idea of in-differentiation: the losing of self into a collective subject. It is this in-differentiation that he refers to as neo-tribalism. With this he is referring to all the "Kiki's", "Punks" and "Paninari's". He calls these sights the specific instances of the ongoing spectacle, which our contemporary urban living has on display. The emphasis is on that which unites rather than on that which divides. In order for this identification to occur, these people identify themselves with the image, a representation that is communal by nature. This is an image, which is identified, adhered to and simultaneously and inevitably expressed in a certain behavior. This image may well belong to an imagined community, which also emphasizes the simultaneity of an image in time. Maffesoli also observes this adherence to be of an ephemeral nature which results in, the process of continual migration between tribes. People, nowadays, are more likely than before to adhere to more than one group simultaneously, even contradictory ones. And people can switch groups with the greatest of ease. Taken from the various research and monographs done on groups of young people, on cliques, and on fashion circles, Maffesoli concludes: "In its various forms, neo-tribalism refuses to be identified with specific political endeavors, does not conform to any single definite structure, and has its sole raison d'être the preoccupation with the collectively lived present" (Maffesoli, 1988). However, it is implied that it is in the rubbing against one another and intermixing by the many little tribes, that Maffesoli recognizes the creation of culture, beliefs and ultimately, behavior.

ACTIVISM, PARTICIPATION, WEAK TIES AND BEHAVIOR CHANGE

There are various theories that explain participation in movements. The Resource Mobilization (RM) theory emphasizes that participation depends on the costs and rewards available (McCarthy & Zald, 1977). These rewards are divided in three types: solidary incentives (emotional rewards, group reinforcements), material incentives (money, goods, services) and purposive incentives (the belief that acts are effective). Particularly concerning rewards, Olson (1965) stresses the rational behind collective action being the selective and individual incentive; without it, collective action would never happen. However, these views have been criticized for its underlying economic assumptions, an underdeveloped account of individual agency and a tendency to overlook a movement's weak support. In "Mobilizing weak support for social movements" Ennis and Schreuer take on a different perspective. They emphasize participants' attitudes, by looking at grievances, especially in considering weak support (Ennis & Schreuer, 1987). They define different levels of support: Core activists, active supporters, weak supporters, the uncommitted and opponents. Concerning the weak support they suggest that less intensive support within the constituency is more pervasive and potentially as important. For this they call up the analogy with Granovetter's notion of weak ties (Granovetter, 1973). Like weak ties, weak support extends outside the boundaries of localized social networks; it can provide channels for persuasion, conversion, and recruitment. They argue that the importance of weak supporters lies in their function in demonstrating the movements' power to potential converts. Also, weak support is more widespread than active support and has therefore a greater ability to reach the uncommitted beyond movement circles; they tend to spread the word. However, in "Weak ties in networked communities", in terms of weak support, Kavanaugh et al suggest that the Internet only creates weak ties (Kavanaugh, 2005). Supporters often choose to move on and do not feel a need to get permanently engaged. It could be suggested that within neo-tribalism, one can zip from one activism group to another. This would emphasize the ephemeral nature of weak ties. Van Laer and Van Aelst point out the lag of Internet

based activism (Van Laer & Van Aelst, 2010). They warn us that anyone with a Facebook profile can form a group against or in favor of a particular cause and invite other members to sign this cause by becoming a member of this group. They conclude that new media, apart from offering opportunities, also carries serious limitation. As an example they give *keyboard activism*, where the low threshold has made joining a low, but made the commitment and effective activity after joining equally low. However, R. Kelly Garrett emphasizes the micro contribution and says that small actions may lead to a greater sense of obligation (Garrett, 2006). This means that an individual who has contributed to a campaign, no matter how limited or small-scale, even if it is simply by joining or "liking" a group on Facebook, is more likely to feel more committed to the issue, which in turn could mean a positive effect on moving beyond the movements boundary, especially if it is noticed by others. It is this effect that may suggest that an event as such has the potential to spread a certain behavior.

ACTIVISM, NEO-TRIBALISM AND INTERNET TECHNOLOGY

Maffesoli argues that the power of the emblematic image associated with tribes has accrued with technological development. This means that Internet and on-line social networks like Facebook are continued to put to work to empower this emblematic image. In "Citizens and activists" Anne Marie Oostveen argues that ICT makes it easier for ideological supporters to get politically involved and become more practical supporters at little cost to them (Oostveen, 2010). However, in "Why social movement sympathizers don't participate" Oegema and Klandermans point out that even though the internet makes it easier for activists to reach people, it does not make it easier for people to participate in movements (Oegema & Klandermans 1994). Nonetheless, there is a consensus on that new technologies are indubitably and increasingly being used for social and cultural change. Anne Marie Oostveen concludes that Internet technology can be used in many ways by grass roots groups; such as educating, building a community, recruit fellow advocates and facilitate mass media coverage. She adds: "It is now cheap, effective and quick to

broadcast information” (Oostveen, 2010). In “Internet and social movement action repertoires”, borrowing from Tilly’s original definition of the action repertoire¹, Van Laer and Van Aelst speak of a new digitalized social movement repertoire of collective action. Within his typology of a new digitalized social movement repertoire of collective action, they address two dimensions, collective action that is Internet supported and actions that are Internet based. The former are old forms of taking action where Internet functions as support. The latter are new forms where Internet is essential to the action. Within this typology they consider consumer activism being Internet supported with a low threshold of participating. They suggest Internet mediated consumer behavior as some kind of a political consumerism. As example they give the fair trade movement. For these movements the Internet provides with important new assets to be exploited. For example, if you intend to boycott certain products or to buy specific food or clothes for ethical or political reasons, you need to be knowledgeable about different alternatives. Here the Internet offers clear advantages in terms of information dissemination.

DATA

In early summer of 2010 a group of friends challenged each other to just to consume at local independent stores for two weeks long.” This seemingly simple appeal proved to be quite challenging in the urban city of Helsinki. One of the friends published this challenge in form of a blog where experiences and stories from this challenge could be shared. Soon friends and acquaintances were invited to write their experiences for the blog. Later he also organized a Facebook group to bring all the participants together. Due to publicity, a prominent local newspaper, the Helsinki Sanomat, picked up the story and published an on-line news article on it, giving it a public profile. It became an event that attracted over 200 participants. In late summer of that same year they decided to do it again. This time a Facebook event was created for

the purpose of distributing the call for participation. The mechanisms of social networking were put to work from the start. The same people of the previous Facebook group were called up to join and to forward the event to their friend networks. This time the event attracted general interest from various smaller lifestyle magazines, which published stories on the event as well. The event peaked at a number of around 900 participants. Something that started out as a private issue grew out to become a public concern and event. This paper concerns the second time of this event.

The organizers of the event were all either friends or friends of friends. The invitations to the event were sent out using their Facebook friends’ networks, here considered as both representing strong ties as well as weak ties. From the 26 participants that joined this study, 9 were male and 17 were female; and 23 people were between the 20 and 35 years old.

In order to understand and to explicate the different aspects of the participants’ experiences of this event, this paper addresses two types of material for research, each representing a different angle to the event. First is the “Call for participation”. This is the invitation and introductory text that the participants see when they join the event. Second is an on-line survey, which is done with the participants. A general strategy of, and the elements for analysis is formulated using Maffesoli’s notion of neo-tribalism. Accordingly to the type of material, methods have been selected for its analysis. The two main methods are: Rhetorical analysis based on the Burke’s concept theory of identification; Content analysis based on open coding.

ANALYSIS

Maffesoli suggests the idea of persona. Within this persona is considered the following: “each individual is a simple punctum of an uninterrupted chain, even attributing to him a multiplicity of facets, each constituting a microcosm, a crystallization, and an expression of the general macrocosm” (Maffesoli, 1988). Methodologically Maffesoli says it is essential “to point out, describe, and analyze the social configurations that seem to go beyond individualism, and to understand the undefined mass, the

¹ Tilly’s definition says: “A repertoire of collective action is the set of means that are effectively available to a given set of people and which they use to act collectively in order to make claims in individuals and groups.”

population without identity, or the tribalism that though nebulous, contains small local units" (Maffesoli, 1988). Maffesoli also points out several elements for analysis: 1) the image and the imagined community, to which the participants adhere and 2) the emergence of strong collective sentiments. This gives us the strategic direction in our analysis, in which both the portrayed image of the event, and the participant with its complexities play a central role. With a qualitative approach this study explores this image, the sentiment, its suggested discourse and the different configurations of the personas.

THE IMAGE OF THE EVENT

The "Call for participation" is the invitation and introductory text that the participants see when they join the event. The emphasis is on investigating 1) what image is represented and 2) how people are being persuaded to join and to act. Complementary questions to this are: How is the appeal designed and how does it make use of the existing associations that people have as the material of design.

According to Burke the basic function of rhetoric, the use of words by human agents, is to form attitudes or to induce actions in other human agents. It is not simply to trying to tell how things are, but it is trying to move people. Burke argues that every text, all images, represent an underlying indication of change, they are receptacles that contain processes of change, indications of transformation. Development and transformation is something he also calls, "the becoming" or "fullfilment" or "fruition". In this process certain techniques can be used to explicate the rhetoric. This paper will address the technique of association and dissociation. The explicated rhetoric illustrates the task ahead and indicates the premise on which action is induced.

"What kind of city do we want: cold and boring, pseudo-cheap chain stores and supermarkets, or do you want to live in the city, where you will be served, where you can affect how and where you shop, which is also ecologically friendly, maybe even employing"²

² The original text, in Finnish, can be found here: <http://www.facebook.com/event.php?eid=133725356643667> or alternatively a copy of the text has been placed here: <http://designresearch.fi/blogs/tjhien/2011/01/how-do-you-get-by-without-retail-chains/>

With this opening sentence the reader is put in a frame of mind: Threat. The threat is not explicitly named, it is implied. The author does not say that the city is or is becoming cold and boring. But he suggests that this might be or is becoming reality. This normative stance continues in series associative successions. The chain supermarket, the target of this event, is being associated with "cold and boring". At the same time the "disappearance of the last independent shop" is associated with the disappearances of our "real choice":

"After the last little shop will be closed, we no longer have a real choice."

It can be inferred that this sentence makes space for the association of the supermarkets with the main threat: losing our freedom of choice. Freedom suddenly becomes the very ambiguous ultimate value that enables the reader to be unified with an otherwise divided audience. An extra appeal to our reason is called upon by associating the supermarket industry with the cinema industry. This infringement allows and attempts to legitimize the act:

"Look at what happened to movie theaters! Now the theaters are in the hands one major player and the selection has not become more diversified ..."

By doing so this article both demonstrates a reality and provides a "model" in which most of us is expected to understand the consequences, if no action is undertaken. With this the author hopes to move the audience.

Subjunctive orientation and symbolic action

In Maffesoli's terms of neo-tribalism the event becomes both individualizing and de-individualizing. With his rhetoric Burke is addressing the essence of persuasion: that of others and that of the self. The following quotation best illustrates and gives force to this relationship. "The individual person, striving to form himself in accordance with the communicative norms that match the cooperative ways of his society, is by the same token concerned with the rhetoric of identification. To act upon himself persuasively, he must variously resort to images and ideas that are formative. Education (Indoctrination)

exerts such pressure upon him from without; he completes the process from within. If he does not somehow act to tell himself (as his own audience) what the various brands of rhetorician have told him, his persuasion is not complete. Only those voices from without are effective which can speak in the language of a voice within" (1950).

With the previous analysis we see that the images the author portrays is addressing certain sentiments, certain values. He does so through a series of associations and disassociations. These values return with the following suggestion for an alternative reality:

"... or do you want to live in the city, where you will be served, where you can affect how and where you shop, which is also ecologically friendly, maybe even employing"

This is a representation of values. Moreover it is a list of "wishes" to which the audience is supposed to adhere. It is a subjunctive orientation. This orientation implies that the city of Helsinki should be a city where you are served, it should be a city where you can affect the way you consume. It is an orientation to which people are supposed to adhere. It provides an important part of the image. And consequently it provides the premises for a subjunctive ritual in which this wish acquires for a period of time a concrete form, at least as long as the event lasts. By doing so the creation of the value becomes a matter of sentiments. It creates a shared sentiment, thus transforming readers, unified into one big audience, a tribe, ready to move on as one. In the transformation the event at once becomes a symbol that simultaneously gets meaning by, as well as, gives meaning to the participant. The event aims at getting the audience into action. At the same time the action becomes symbolic.

PARTICIPANT SURVEYS

The survey existed of a series of questionnaires, which were conducted during the event with 26 participants. These questionnaires addressed the participant's view on the event, their motivations of joining and their expectations. The questionnaires also addressed how the participants experienced the event and how the event affected their practices in daily life. This is done by means of a content analysis

using open coding. The purpose of this analysis is to explicate participant's understanding of the event and the way the event affected their lives. The following questions were used: 1) Why did you participate in the event? 2) What are your expectations of the coming two weeks? 3a) What was enjoyable about the event? And 3b) What was annoying about the event? The event lasted for two weeks. The survey was spread over three weeks. The survey existed of five on-line questionnaires, divided in two types: "the experience-questionnaire", that asked a mix of open questions and closed questions concerning the event experience, and "the topic-questionnaire", that asked only open questions. The "topic questionnaire" asked the participant to reflect deeper on a health related topic. The sequence of questionnaires is illustrated in table 1.

In total 100 people were addressed randomly³ from the Facebook event page. Sourcing of people happened two weeks before the event started, so people that joined after that were mostly not taken into account. From the 100 people 31 people agreed to join the study of which 26 participants replied the first survey.⁴ These people were mostly young professionals in and around the metropolitan area of Helsinki. The participants were promised a reward at the end of the survey. To motivate the participants to continue the survey, they were rewarded with bits of information during the survey. With every questionnaire, except for the first one, the email contained some preliminary findings of the previous questionnaire⁵. The survey was analyzed through content analysis based on open coding. Through open

³ These people were picked from the guest list, as ordered as Facebook does. Although nobody would deny the importance of these types of social media today, the author of this paper acknowledges the remaining discussion on using Facebook as a means for these type of studies. Concerning sampling, this is far from random. Certain identifiers like age, education, level of interest for food, could be said to be highly homogenous.

⁴ Out of 31 people 26 people answered the first questionnaire, 17 people answered the second, 19 answered the third, 16 answered the fourth and 17 answered the fifth. Out of 31 people 10 people completed all questionnaires, 8 people completed 4 and 7 completed 3 or less. The questionnaires skipped were different per person. However, for the purpose of this paper the answers given, even though the participant did not complete all questionnaires, are still considered accountable. The participants were Finnish native speakers. The survey was done in English.

⁵ This was done to increase engagement amongst participants. However, these were selected in consideration, to prevent bias as much as possible in the continuing survey.

coding various themes surfaced. This resulted in an organization of themes. Three themes were chosen for further discussion in this paper: 1) Indignation, 2) expectations and 3) Planning the event.

The rhetoric of the call for participation was also compared with the themes from the survey. The purpose of this analysis is to gain a better understanding in the individual expectations and actions in relationship with the collective image. We are reminded that an individual remains a distinct and unique individual with individual motives. The individual is in the same instant “identified with” and “different from” others.

Week	Questionnaire type
Week prior to event	Experience questionnaire 1
Beginning week 1	Topic questionnaire 1
End week 1	Experience questionnaire 2
Beginning week 2	Topic questionnaire 2
End week 2	Experience questionnaire 3

Table 1: Sequence of the survey Week

Collective sentiment: indignation

According to Burke rhetoric is the art of persuasion. Burke (1950) says: “we might well keep in mind that a speaker persuades an audience by the use of stylistic identifications; his act of persuasion may be for the purpose of causing the audience to identify itself with the speakers interests.” The identification, the voice from within, in question here is indignation. Many of the participants expressed their indignation towards what appears to be the domination of the distribution of foods by mainly two food distributors in the supermarket industry in Helsinki, Finland. This dominance is associated with the impoverishment of the urban street image and livelihood and an impoverished selection of goods. Many participants also express their support for the independent retailer and “little shops”.

“I think it's a good challenge for myself and it's definitely positive to find other ways to get by than always ending up in the same retail chains - especially concerning food. It's also stupid and wrong that the whole food market is mainly controlled by three to four chains - HOK-Elanto, Tradeka, Kesko and Lidl.... People including me should support little shops way more than they do now.”

“It was a bit difficult, but also eye-opening... hadn't really thought on how dependent I am on retail chains.”

Being in the know and not being in the know

Two classifications of groups emerged from the data. The first group that was already familiar with the “little shops” and the second group that was not. The first group was already practicing shopping at “little shops”. For them it was easy to avoid large retail chains and to live through the event, since their life was already “routinized” that way. This group was well known with the controversy around large retail chains in Helsinki and knew exactly where to shop. When asked about their expectations, they simply answered:

“I do not expect anything to change.” Or:

“I expect to eat as I do now. Fresh vegetables, little bit of good meats and fish...”

“Actually I don't shop in the big supermarkets anyway. Lots of veggies and seafood.”

Although most participants cherished strong interest for food, this was particularly the case for this group. They also tended to categorize their diet as being healthy. However, the second group of participants mentioned the challenge being the reason for joining. This challenge expressed itself in different ways. For a large number of people joining this event meant “to try out different ways to live”, “to discover new things” and “doing something different”. It may “add something to their daily life”.

“I like to try different ways to live. I thought it would be interesting to try living without retail chains and see if it really is more expensive to buy food from small markets that sell products from local farmers.”

“I was invited by a friend and got interested to join, because I always do grocery shopping at my nearest supermarket and don't often go to special stores. This makes my day more interesting and maybe I get new experiences and try things I wouldn't otherwise even think.”

“I probably have walked past those [independent retailer] many times without noticing them as I have not been looking for those.”

To the closed question on to what degree they will eat more or less healthy during the event, a bit more than half answered “as healthy as I do now.” The other half answered either “a bit more healthy” or “Much more healthy.” However, to the open question on their expectations around their food consumption during the event most of them

mentioned “more fresh/local/organic ingredients” or “More better tasting/quality/healthy food.”

“I think there is going to be more fresh stuff in my diet.”

“I think I’ll be eating lot more berries and vegetables because I will be using much more marketplaces.”

“I hope this will have a lasting impact on my diet, I want to get rid of all (or at least most of) the junk food, which has always been the all-too-easy option.”

“I expect to get a little better quality food and more organic food.”

This suggests that the event is associated with a practice of food consumption that is more associated with healthier and tastier kind of food: Better food. It could be suggested that this forms an important part of the image of the event, which is also an image to which these participants prefer to adhere to. It becomes an aspiration, thus knowing how to acquire this kind of food becomes the observed issue. Two groups of participants emerge: 1) those that are in the know and 2) those that are not.

Practicing the event: How will it fit one’s life

The interesting participants for this paper are those that are relatively new to the practice of shopping at smaller and independent stores. For these people the event would indicate a real change in behavior. From these, many considered how the event would affect their daily routines. Some concerns were mentioned on a possible conflict with their working hours. Some participants simply do not live close to any independent retail stores, making them plan these “trips” more than usual.

“I find it interesting to see whether I’ll be able to do this. My working hours doesn’t allow the shopping usually nowhere else than in the retail chains. There are stores that are not part of the retail chains in the area which I always wanted to visit but never get there during the workdays.”

“I have no independent, small grocery stores nearby where I live. I do some grocery shopping already now in small, independent stores on my way from work but I do wonder whether I have time to do all shopping in these stores.”

“I think I might have to alter my diet a bit according to what’s available at markets and stores. Also, I reckon I have to think about more what to get and where.”

The experience of planning appears to be both a blessing and a curse. Some people mention it being a positive experience, enhancing awareness of their

consumption. Others mention it being a negative experience, hindering one’s life.

“The fact that I had to plan my eating better turned my diet to a healthier direction.”

“Getting to know the local small stores, and also having to put more effort into grocery. It made the whole thing much more rewarding.”

“The extra planning was difficult in the beginning. Also I did visit a retail-chain shop a couple times when I got tired with the strain of shopping further. Some products were also hard to find.”

“The most annoying thing must have been hopping from shop to another hunting for several ingredients. It takes more time and effort.”

DISCUSSION

Michel Maffesoli speaks of neo tribalism, in which people adhere to certain images, certain ephemeral communities. “The multiplicity of this or that type inevitably favors the emergence of a strong collective sentiment” (Maffesoli, 1988). This event indicates a way of life of acting-together. In doing so, acting-together, the event simultaneously derives its meaning and gives meaning. The event becomes symbolic action; it becomes a symbol, a symbol to which people are able to adhere, identify themselves with and, at the same time, transform themselves with. Such communities are imagined, but clearly not imaginary. Members of this community may or, more likely, may never meet each other face to face. They exist only as shared ideas but this does not make them any less real. In this case it is not just an image that is transmitted but also a shared activity, a behavior. However, it is not the activity of shopping which bonds these strangers, but shopping for the same kind of food in the same kind of stores.

Facebook belongs to the digitalized repertoire of action. Not just in terms of activism but also in terms neo-tribalism. The event uses Facebook to extend its power, to aggregate, to supply it with more people. It could be suggested that neo-tribalism, through Facebook, gives rise to a group of weak supporters, who otherwise would have gone unnoticed. It suggests that this support, this tribe, could be a group citizen life-stylers, in which participating in single issue campaigns forms an important activity, ritual, to commune with others with similar interests. The act of joining this tribe forms the premise of a commitment that may or may

not be of an ephemeral nature. This commitment may or may not lead to a degree of effective action. For those converted in this way, this commitment, in a varying degree, is an encouragement to a change in behavior

NEO-TRIBALISM AND THE TRANSMISSION OF BEHAVIOR

This study suggests this particular event to be, what Maffesoli observes, a “specific instance of the ongoing spectacle” that our urban living has to offer. This makes room for speculation to what degree this event is a form of activism at all, or another form of a tribe where people can join in, not only because of the public political idealistic reasons that are behind it, but also because of various private idiosyncratic reasons that may or may not relate to the cause of activism. Most likely it is both, one not excluding the other, or even acting in concert with each other, one providing the premise for the other and vice versa. This also suggests the inseparable relationship between public concerns and private issues, which deserves more investigation within design.

This study illustrates that the event provides an ideal and with this idea comes a form of behavior. This behavior expresses knowledge, ones capability in conscious shopping, ones informed-ness: being in the know. The knowledge expresses itself in a form of shopping behavior, which is transmittable, communicable, and identifiable. Being in the know would be an attribute on which people can identify others, and through others themselves. Design could facilitate this communication. It remains difficult to attribute this kind of a celebration to appearance only. Perhaps it calls up what Maffesoli says on “place”: Localism. Knowledge is expressed in a behavior. Behavior, in turn takes place at certain places. And these places are occupied by tribes. Small grocery stores become those places where tribes will appear and identify each other’s appearance in form of this behavior. Sharing the behavior becomes the Maffesolian esthetic, the collective experience.

DESIGNING EVENTS WITH BEHAVIOR FOR BEHAVIOR

Louridas describes design as fundamentally a human activity, something people do on a daily basis. Design

is a distinctive human activity, but not so distinct. An event as such is designed. The rhetoric is crafted. It makes use of sentiments, that material at hand which affects people’s motivations. However, study shows that the eventual behavior will be idiosyncratic, leading to different forms and degrees of change. The event will be experienced in ways that are hard to anticipate.

Study identifies the emergence of two main categories of practices within the group: “Those who are in the know” and “Those who are not.” Those, who already shop at small independent shops and those who do not. A twin-group organization as such presents a potential for collective transmission of behavior and thus affecting the collective and individual behaviors, where the behavior of one, “Those who are in the know” influences the other, “Those who are not”. This suggests that an event, as such, is able to change existing behavior and create new behaviors amongst groups, thus changing them in behavior. This makes the event a powerful means for design, especially when we speak of design in relation with designing for behavior change or lifestyle change: Designing with behavior for behavior.

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